

NOTES

Preparation of Glycidic Esters from (+)-Ethyl α -Chloro- α -(2-Methyl Butyl) Acetate through Darzen Condensation

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Milas and coworkers¹ used sodium ethoxide as condensing agent in the reaction of α -halo-esters with β -ionone at -30 to -60° . The present authors have preferred sodium amide keeping a temperature of about 15° . Newman and Magerlein² suggested that only chloroesters are very reactive and when sodium amide is employed as condensing agent, the ethyl ester should be preferred to methyl ester. The present work uses optically active ethyl α -chloro- α -(2-methyl butyl) acetate as the halogenohydrin producing component in the Darzen Glycidic ester condensation with various ketones, preferentially of aliphatic series.

(+)- α -(2-methyl butyl)-acetic acid obtained by the method of Thaker and Pathak³ was chlorinated and esterified to yield (+)-ethylchloro- α -(2-methyl butyl) acetate, $[\alpha]_D^{32} +1.47$. This compound (0.1M) was condensed with ketones (0.1M) such as acetophenone, methyl ethyl ketone, methyl n-propyl ketone, methyl iso-butyl ketone, methyl n-amyl ketone, methyl n-hexyl ketone, ethyl n-butyl ketone, ethyl n-amyl ketone and ethyl iso. amyl ketone (table I). It was found advantageous to use slight excess (0.12M) of sodium amide

Preparation of (+)- α -chloro- α -(2-methyl butyl) acetic acid: Red phosphorous (7.8 g.) and (+)- α -(2-methyl butyl) acetic acid³ (130 g.:1M) were placed in a three necked flask with a gas distribution tube. The flask was heated to 100° and slow stream of pure dry chlorine gas was passed. The gas is passed till there is an increase of 34 gms in weight. The contents of the flask were distilled under vacuum collecting the above chloro acid at $140-142^\circ/20-22\text{mm}$; yield 69%. d_4^{32} 1.080; n_D^{32} 1.4170; $[\alpha]_D^{32} +1.593$ (1,1). Found Cl, 21.82%; M, 166.3; $C_7H_{13}ClO_2$ required Cl, 21.58%; M, 165.5.

Preparation of (+) ethyl- α -chloro- α -(2-methyl butyl) acetate: To a 1000 ml round bottomed flask fitted with Dean and Stark apparatus, the upper end of which was attached with a double surface condenser, were placed the (+)- α -chloro- α -(2-methyl butyl)-acetic acid (165 g.), dry benzene (150 ml), absolute ethyl alcohol (225 ml) and sulphuric acid (2 ml). The contents were refluxed on water-bath for six to seven hours. When no more water separated the esterification was assumed to be completed.

1. Milas and Co-workers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1584.
2. Newman and Magerlein, *Org. reaction*, vol. 5, p. 413, John Wiley and Sons, Inc. Longman Chapman and Hall Ltd, 1949.
3. Thaker and Pathak, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 110.

The contents were then washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (250 ml; 2%) and dried (magnesium sulphate). After removal of benzene, (+)-ethyl α -chloro- α -2-(methyl butyl) acetate was collected at 144-145°/25 mm., yield 67.3%, d_4^{25} ; 0.9849; n_D^{25} 1.4090; (α)_D²⁵+1.47 (1,1). Found; Cl, 18.12%; C₉H₁₇ClO₂ required Cl, 18.44 %).

TABLE I

Specific rotation of the optically active glycidic esters by Darzen condensation

Sr. No.	Name of the Glycidic ester.	Molecular Formula	B.P. ^o 2-3mm.	Specific Rotation [α] _D ²⁵
1.	α -(2-methyl butyl) β -methyl glycidate.	$C_{13}H_{24}O_3$	88-91	+2.21.
2.	α -(2-methyl butyl) β -n-propyl glycidate.	$C_{14}H_{26}O_3$	92-94	+1.73
3.	α -(2-methyl butyl) β -ethyl glycidate	$C_{15}H_{28}O_3$	98-101	+1.92
4.	α -(2-methyl butyl) β -methyl glycidate	$C_{16}H_{30}O_3$	118-119	+2.01
5.	α -(2-methyl butyl) β -methyl glycidate	$C_{17}H_{32}O_3$	123-125	+2.19
6.	α -(2-methyl butyl) β -ethyl glycidate	$C_{16}H_{30}O_3$	114-117	+2.39
7.	α -(2-methyl butyl) β -ethyl glycidate	$C_{17}H_{32}O_3$	133-135	+1.97
8.	α -(2-methyl butyl) β -ethyl glycidate.	$C_{17}H_{32}O_3$	128-130	+2.11
9.	α -(2-methyl butyl) glycidate.	$C_{16}H_{22}O_3$	158-162	+1.86

General method for the preparation of optically active Glycidic esters by Darzen Condensation: To a mixture of carbonyl compound (0.1M) (+)-ethyl α -chloro- (2-methyl butyl) acetate (19.25 g.; 0.1M) and pure benzene (20 ml) in a three-necked flask, fitted with a stirrer and a thermometer, was added over a period of two hours, finely pulverized sodium amide (4.68 g.). The temperature was kept at 10 to 15°; ammonia was evolved. After an hour the contents became very viscous, some more benzene (25 ml) was added and on completion of the addition of sodium amide, the mixture was poured on cracked ice with stirring.

The organic layer was separated and aqueous layer extracted with benzene (75 ml): The combined organic layer and the benzene extract were washed with water (200 ml \times 3), and acetic acid (10 ml) and dried (sodium sulphate). After removal of the solvent, the residue was fractionated under reduced pressure to obtain the desired product.

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